

Improved vision-based weed classification for robotic weeding – a method for increasing speed while retaining accuracy

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Abstract

In this paper, we demonstrate how a deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) can be deployed in resource limited environments, such as robots, to reduce the inference time by more than an order of magnitude while retaining high classification accuracy and robustness to novel conditions. This is achieved by training a lightweight DCNN, or compressed model, via *model distillation*. We show that training models using this approach outperform training a similar model from scratch, using the same data, for weed classification. Using *model distillation* we are able to improve the accuracy from 97.1% to 97.9% for similar conditions (as the training data) and from 86.4% to 89.8% for different conditions (as the training data). This is in comparison to a traditional approach using robust local binary pattern features which achieves 87.7% for classifying in similar conditions and 83.9% for classifying in different conditions. Finally, we compare this compressed model to a complex fine-tuned model which achieves higher accuracy of 99.6% for the same condition and 95.8% for different conditions but has 100.0 times more parameters (larger model size) and is 40.6 times slower at computing the inference.

Background

Deploying robots in agriculture is rapidly gaining interest, this is exemplified by the advent of weed management robots such as AgBot II (Bawden et al. 2017) and harvesting platforms such as Harvey (Lehnert et al. 2017), see Figure 3. These robots are enabled through the use of robotic vision algorithms that let them to perceive and understand the diverse and challenging environments in which they operate. For example, AgBot II uses robotic vision to first detect vegetation and then to classify the weed species whilst harvesting robots, such as Harvey, segments the crop from the background and use this information to harvest successfully. A key robotic vision tool of increasing importance is the use of models trained using deep learning.

Figure 3. Left is an image of AgBot II and right is an image of Harvey

The advent of deep learning (LeCun et al. 2015), and in particular deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs), has made it possible to solve challenging problems such as weed classification (fine-grained classification) and crop detection (semantic segmentation). This has been achieved through advances in machine learning that make it possible to learn discriminative features and has the potential to obviate the need to hand craft features for each task. Yet, there are two issues that are stymying the widespread adoption of these techniques in challenging domains such as

agricultural robotics, these are: (i) it is difficult to train a DCNN from limited data and (ii) many state-of-the-art networks are complex and large making their deployment on resource limited robotic computer hardware difficult. One approach to overcome the first point has been to make use of transfer learning (Yosinski et al. 2014) where a model trained for one task (e.g. general object classification) using millions of image is then adapted to a new task using relatively few images (typically thousands). To be successful, transfer learning is typically applied to large models such as Inception-v3 and VGG. This leads to the second point, regarding the deployment of large and higher-fidelity models, even the relatively small Inception-v3 model consists of 25M parameters which is small compared to the 180M parameters for VGG (Szegedy et al. 2015, McCool et al. 2017).

Similar to our recently proposed work (McCool et al. 2017), in this work we explore the potential to use a compressed model to develop an efficient classifier for weed classification; in our previous work we performed weed segmentation. Using a compressed model allows us to trade off complexity (e.g. memory size and speed) against classification accuracy. Using this approach leads to impressive results with our classifier able to achieve an accuracy of 97.9% for the same condition (as the training data) and 89.8% for different conditions (as the training data). This is in comparison to a traditional approach using robust local binary pattern features which achieves 87.7% for classifying in the same condition and 83.9% for classifying in different conditions. Finally, we compare this compressed model to a more complex fine-tuned model (derived through transfer learning) which achieves higher accuracy of 99.6% for the same condition and 95.8% for different conditions but has 100.0 times more parameters (model size) and is 40.6 times slower for inference.

Methods

To train a compressed DCNN we apply the following two-step process:

1. We apply transfer learning to fine-tune a pre-trained model to the task at hand, in this case weed classification. Concretely, we fine-tune the Inception-v3 (Szegedy et al. 2015) model and refer to this fine-tuned model as Adapted-IV3. The process for adaptation is described in more detail below.
 - The adapted model, Adapted-IV3, is then used to *teach* (train) a much smaller (lightweight) DCNN. The way in which the adapted network is used to teach the smaller network is described in more detail below.

In this work, we apply model compression to the task of weed classification, where a bounding box is provided and the species of weed (vegetation) present needs to be classified. In previous work (McCool et al. 2017) we used a similar approach to perform rapid weed segmentation which is a per-pixel two-class problem (weed or not weed) whereas weed classification is a *C*-class classification problem, which of the *C* classes is this particular weed.

Transfer learning: adapting complex pre-trained networks

It is often difficult to train a DCNN from limited data and, as mentioned above, one approach to overcome this is to make use of transfer learning (Yosinski et al. 2014). Transfer learning is where a model trained for one task (e.g. general object classification) using millions of images is then adapted to a new task using relatively few images (typically thousands). This is a common approach and it was shown in (Ge et al. 2015) that when there is limited data to train a network from scratch it is better practice to take a pre-trained network and then apply transfer learning to fine-tune it for the task at hand.

We apply transfer learning to fine-tune a GoogLeNet Inception-v3 (Szegedy et al. 2015) architecture which consists of 25M parameters. The ImageNet dataset, using 1,000 classes each with 1,000 images, was used to pre-train this model. The structure of the Inception-v3 model was derived for mobile applications, as such it has a relatively low number of parameters, consisting of just 25M parameters. However, this is still quite a complex model. In order to reduce model complexity, and thus the number of parameters (as well as inference speed), we apply model compression. In this case, the fine-tuned Inception-v3 model acts as the *teacher*.

Transfer learning is performed by upsampling the original images to match the template required by the Inception-v3 architecture which is (an image). The original image resolutions are usually square images of size pixels.

Model compression: training lightweight DCNNs

To perform model compression, we take the approach that we previously described in (McCool et al. 2017) where we first fine-tune a complex pre-trained model to the particular task at hand, this is the *teacher* network. A lightweight *student* DCNN is then learnt from this complex model.

The *teacher* network is trained using the upsampled images, with a window size of. This network produces a logit output which is obtained prior to applying the softmax operation. By contrast, the *student* network takes as input a smaller image size, it also produces a logit output. For our experiments we set. To train the *student* the classification loss (between the *student* and groundtruth) was used in combination with the loss between and. This training scheme forces the *student* to represent the input signal (image) in a manner similar to the *teacher* while also ensuring that the classification accuracy is optimised.

By using a lower resolution image to train the *student* network we make the underlying structure of this network much less complex than the original fine-tuned network. This leads to considerable improvements in terms of the memory footprint as well as the time required to perform inference.

Results

We apply our approach to the problem of weed classification on a robotic platform, in this case AgBot II. Example images of the plants being classified and the challenging conditions are given in Figure 4. All of our models were implemented in Tensorflow v0.10 using a GeForce Titan X graphics card. A learning rate of was used with the AdamOptimizer in conjunction with a mini-batch size of 60 images and a dropout rate of 50%. The lightweight DCNNs were trained using the same data as was used to fine-tune the complex (Inception-v3) network and are referred to as AgNet. We compare our DCNN system to the classifier recently proposed by Bawden et al. (2017) which uses a local binary pattern (LBP) features. We use these features to train a random forest class, this system is referred to as LBP RF.

The results in Table IV highlight the potential improvements available by using the compressed DCNN, AgNet, solution. The compressed DCNN consistently outperforms the traditional features such as the LBP RF approach. Furthermore, it outperforms training a DCNN from scratch, referred to as the WeedNet system, which achieves an accuracy of 97.1% vs 97.9% when testing in similar conditions and 86.4% vs 89.8% for testing in different conditions. The similar conditions are on weed images taken from a test field with only a few weeks difference. The different conditions are on weed images take from a test field with plants grown 3 months later. The compressed DCNN solution also presents several advantages over using the fine-tuned system, Adapted-IV3.

Table IV. Weed classification results for the different systems.

	Testing Conditions) (Similar	Testing Conditions) (Different	Num. Parameters	Regions per Second
Adapted-IV3	99.6%	95.8%	25M	155
AgNet	97.9%	89.8%	0.25M	6,300
WeedNet	97.1%	86.4%	0.25M	6,300
LBP RF	87.7%	83.9%	N/A	N/A

When comparing the AgNet system against the Adapted-IV3 system we note that although it has lower accuracy it has considerable advantages in terms of complexity (especially speed). The Adapted-IV3 model has an accuracy of with 99.6% vs 97.9% for AgNet on similar testing conditions and 95.8% vs 89.8% when testing in different conditions. However, this higher accuracy comes at a considerably increase computational cost. The Adapted-IV3 classifier can only process 155 regions per second, whereas, AgNet can process 6,300 regions per second. This is a speed improvement of 40.6 times faster. Second, the memory footprint of AgNet is 100.0 times less than the Adapted-IV3 system. This means that the AgNet could be deployed easily to hardware-resource deprived situations such as robotic systems, remote sensors and even mobile phones.

Figure 4. Example images of the weeds that need to be classified. From left to right, two images of cotton, followed by two images of wild oats, finally two images of sowthistle. These images highlight the challenging illumination conditions as well as the considerable changes in plant structure that can occur as illustrated by the two images of sowthistle.

Discussion

We have presented an efficient method to which uses compressed DCNN which have the potential to be deployed in resource limited environments such as robots, remote sensors and even mobile phones. Key to training these models is to *distill* the knowledge from a complex pre-trained model which acts as a teacher. This *teacher* is used to train a *student* DCNN which is much smaller.

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